

REBOOT

EUROPEAN FILM COMPETITIVENESS

Policy briefings

deriving from WP2-5

Project: Reviving, Boosting, Optimising and Transforming European Film Competitiveness - REBOOT

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1 PROJECT SUMMARY

This project aims to connect the existing strengths, identify and overcome weaknesses and plan for future competitiveness in the fields of policy, practice and experience. More concretely, the project's objectives are, on the one hand, to explore the long-standing strengths and pervasive gaps in European competitiveness and policies for competitiveness. This includes ways of 'measuring' 'analysing' and 'evaluating' the impact of policies and strategic pathways. On the other hand, the project aspires to place attention to the active preparation for the future in the area of audiences by exploring audience preferences and their generation, as well as modes of film content production. The latter are elements which today's youth will carry and engage with in the coming decades as makers and consumers, as well as industry and policy leaders. Therefore, the consortium interrogates not only the 'what is' but also the 'what has been' and 'what will be' with fresh lenses. REBOOT's ambition is to provide a full set of knowledge of the European film industry, which maximises its existing strengths, combined with strategic and tactical dimensions of action for the optimisation of the potential held in European youth publics, understood both as emerging audiences and as citizens. Specifically, the ambition of the project combines several dimensions, which reinforce each other but are listed separately for analytical purposes (and in no particular order): a) increasing support for young people's engagement with European film; b) strengthening the place of the EU in the global audiovisual economy, particularly in light of the rise of video on demand (VOD); c) supporting cultural diversity in the EU film industry; d) addressing the need for a different understanding of competitiveness and relevant indicators in this context; and e) recognising and supporting the importance for the EU of film and, more broadly, of the cultural and creative sector as a geopolitical asset.

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

2 PURPOSE OF THIS DOCUMENT

This Document contains Policy Briefs and Recommendations that emerged from WP2 – WP5

The following policy briefs are provided:

Engagement and Inclusion of Young People in the European Film Industry: Katharine Sarikakis (UNIVIE),
Gentiana Ramadani (UNIVIE), Janina Juengst (UNIVIE), Angeliki Chatziefrimidou (UNIVIE) - WP5 4

Fostering 'competitiveness' and 'cultural diversity' in the European film and audiovisual sector: Evangelia
Psychogiopoulou (ELIAMEP), Apostolos Samaras (ELIAMEP), Laia Comerma (ELIAMEP), Antonios Vlassis
(ULIEGE), Dealan Riga (ULIEGE) - WP2 & WP3 13

Pathway to the Operationalisation of the Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage: Unravelling
the Copyright-Related Aspects of Populating the Data Space with Cinematographic Works: Caterina
Sganga(SSSA), Pelin Turan (SSSA) - WP6 21

Developing young people's Engagement with European Cinema via the Youth Audience Award: Tuuli
Lähdesmäki (JYU), Kaisa Hiltunen (JYU) - WP5 35

Policy Brief

January 2024

Engagement and Inclusion of Young People in the European Film Industry

Katharine Sarikakis (UNIVIE), Angeliki Chatzieframidou (UNIVIE),
Gentiana Ramadani (UNIVIE), and Janina Juengst (UNIVIE)

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

Who is this aimed at

Relevant to the European Film Industry:

- EU and national Policymakers
- Government and local Authorities
- Industry Stakeholders
- Educational institutions
- Youth organisations

Key messages

- Young people are the future of creativity and innovation in the European Creative Industries; their perspectives and talents have the potential to rejuvenate and reshape the European film industry (EFI). The involvement of youth in the EFI is not only beneficial, but also crucial for ensuring relevance and dynamism of the EFI in storytelling.
- Spaces, systems and measures in developing the competitiveness of EFI should include provisions for young filmmakers to experiment independently, so that youth's diverse living experience and perspectives find authentic expression and validation.
- Pre-industry initiatives aim to educate emerging media creators in collaborative creativity across diverse backgrounds to challenge established norms within the industry. These initiatives play a pivotal role in nurturing emerging talent, providing young creators with spaces to experiment, develop skills, demonstrate creativity, and develop networks. These programmes must be strengthened to encourage creative collaboration among young people from diverse and non socioeconomic dominant backgrounds who can challenge and redefine industry norms.
- Systematically engaging young people in decision-making processes governing the EFI, ensures that content remains relevant, youth participate in political and civic education, and the EFI creates spaces that resonate with young people's multifaceted interests and values. This can ensure a more robust and future-oriented development of the sector.

Introduction

The European audiovisual industries, including EFI, need reinforcement to enhance young people's competitiveness in the global market (Mitric & Sarikakis, 2016). As we navigate the evolving landscape of media and entertainment, there is a growing recognition of the untapped potential and perspectives

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that youth brings to the table. Engaging young people in the film industry is not merely about diversifying the talent pool, but also about rejuvenating storytelling, fostering innovation, and challenging the conventional norms that have shaped the industry for decades (Sarikakis, Ramadani & Juengst, forthcoming). The EFI is faced with the challenge of directly including young talent in relevant policies. Youth represent an important part of the audience (British Film Institute “BFI”, 2018) and its future consumer base and it is necessary to consider and respond to their interests and needs. Promoting a proactive approach that encourages young people’s participation, including in decision-making, is essential.

Additionally, encouraging education and interest for the film industry from an early age is crucial to sustaining and growing the industry not only as an audience, but also as young, aspiring professionals in the field. Therefore, pre-industry initiatives have a distinct advantage in training emerging media creators to collaborate creatively across diverse backgrounds, challenging the existing norms of the industry. A pre-industry programme is understood as an advanced stage of development in higher education initiatives aimed at professionally instructing students in media production. Characterised by a collaborative relationship between educational institutions and various media industries, such programmes typically encompass film, radio, and television. The focus is on preparing students for future roles in the media sector by providing comprehensive training and practical experiences that bridge the gap between academic learning and industry demands (Banks, 2019).

This policy brief explores the ways in which empowering youth as catalysts in the EFI, emphasising pre-industry programmes and strategies to lower entry barriers, can support and ensure a commercially vibrant and socially inclusive future of the film industry.

Statement of the problem

In the 2000s, European Union (EU) institutions undertook a series of initiatives to enhance audiovisual policies (EC, 2012; EC, 2013), specifically focussing on the film and media industry in Europe (EP and CoE. 2014). With a particular focus on the film sector, evaluation criteria for state aid for the production of films and other audiovisual works were developed in 2001, emphasising economic considerations, primarily (EC, 2013). The European Commission’s policies predominantly reflect the classic model of economic development, often overlooking cultural and creative growth. Historically, there is a noticeable omission regarding the inclusion of young people as creators and leaders in the film sector. To understand the role of young people in the broader policies of European institutions concerning the film sector, it is essential first to examine the weight European Commission assigns to policies for this

community and the ways in which influential stakeholders in the EFI perceive, interpret, and address the challenges associated with market transformation, particularly regarding young individuals as upcoming collaborators in the industry.

Recent research points to the untapped potential within Europe concerning the engagement of young individuals with the EFI. In 2021, a study encompassing 937 young people across eight European nations, found a predominant trend among youth, as they overwhelmingly opt for consuming movies at home through personal devices and a discernible preference for U.S. American film productions over their European counterparts (Soto-Sanfiel et al., 2021). These findings point to the need for heightened efforts in promoting film literacy and educating young people about European heritage in the film industry. This includes the need to address and help reshape the attitudes of young individuals towards European films, particularly regarding their role as an important audience demographic (BFI, 2018), emphasising the necessity to cultivate a greater appreciation and interaction with local cinematic creations (Soto-Sanfiel et al., 2021). Moreover, these indications point to the need to inspire, include and enthuse young people about the possibilities and potential of European filmmaking. A persisting challenge, which needs to be addressed, is the lack of educational opportunities, as current education systems do not prioritise learning and understanding film for young people. This deficiency remains, despite differences between countries and educational institutions, highlighting the need for a Europe-wide, transnational approach to film education (BFI, 2012). Furthermore, there is an urgent need for greater awareness of the preferences of the younger demographic. While factors, such as sound and image quality, ticket prices, and sanitary conditions influence cinema attendance (Tintel & Raats, 2022), a more in-depth understanding of young communities is essential. Research into young people's cinema habits across eight different European countries has raised concerns and shown that youth's interest in cinema is decreasing compared to previous years (Soto-Sanfiel et al., 2021), with going to the cinema being a sporadic and not a preferred activity (Veenstra, 2017). Cinema going is a financial burden for young people and the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic has made young people reluctant to return to traditional cinema experiences (Tintel & Raats, 2022).

Moreover, addressing young people as aspiring professionals within the film industry, reveals several challenges that hinder their participation in this field. A notable issue is the lack of stimulation of interest, where the absence of structured programmes in the European curriculum leaves emerging professionals without the necessary experience of producer roles in relevant projects (McSheaffrey, 2020). This deficiency not only affects the development of youth's technical skills, but also the promotion of their creativity, resulting in a lack of active involvement of young people in film production (McSheaffrey, 2020).

Additionally, another significant obstacle is the lack of opportunities for young people to enter the industry. While European policies provide for workplace safety for youth, there is a gap in enabling entry into the industry, forcing young professionals to both obscurity and precarity. Limited

opportunities to establish themselves professionally in the film industry further exacerbate the problem, as young people encounter obstacles in receiving adequate work assignments and compensation for their roles as directors, screenwriter and audiovisual authors (Willekens et al., 2019).

The film industry has the potential to foster a transformative space, especially for young filmmakers to engage in socio-political discourses by using their cinematic creations as an opportunity for advocacy and change. These developments, which include various advanced film tools, serve not only as instruments for artistic creation, but also as powerful mediums for social activism and personal expression (Sarikakis, Ramadani & Juengst, forthcoming), facilitated by new ways of distributions, enabling direct audience interaction by triggering discussions about politically relevant themes. Enabling young people to create films about their own views and experiences is essential for future development (Cybart-Persenaire & Literat, 2018). This includes not only the development of skills such as collaboration, but also the promotion of self-expression and exploration, especially for diverse, marginalised and multilingual young people. In addition, this can help foster young people's political and civic development by using their own voice and recognising the power of that voice in civic spaces. By combining their personal and creative interests with public activism, young people can link political participation with filmmaking as a tool for expression.

As the narratives portrayed on our screens should represent the diverse fabric of our society, these narratives deeply influence self-perception, lifestyles, and perceptions of others. For many, the depictions offered by these industries serve as their primary or even sole representation, whether these portrayals are authentic or misleading.

The expansive scope and potential for growth within the film and media industries means that there appears to be a degree of exclusion of young people from the overarching narrative. However, European initiatives and practices funded by European resources offer a contrasting picture. Institutions are increasingly dedicated to promoting the film and media sector, with a specific emphasis on involving young individuals. Robust programmes, such as MEDIA 2007-14 and 2014-2020, operating within a broader framework supporting media industries, particularly film and television, are instrumental in this effort. Meanwhile, youth participates in a range of activities, including training programmes, collaborative ventures, festivals, and what is referred to as the pre-industry sector, providing young professionals with opportunities to develop skills and become proficient collaborators. Providing hope and an example towards the right direction, a recent illustration of the inclusion of young individuals in such programmes is the establishment of "The Future of European Film, co-created by Young People" within the European Film Awards Academy in November 2023. Throughout the year, the European Film Academy contributes in various activities that encompass film policy, economic factors, artistic endeavours, and training aspects. These activities involve conferences, seminars, and workshops, all aimed at bridging the gap between creativity and the industry.

Policy recommendations to empower youth as catalysts in the EFI

1. Make Youth-Centric Policy to address shortfalls in Europe's film sphere

The problems faced by young people in the EFI are multifaceted, encompassing structural limitations, financial constraints, and institutional barriers. To address these issues, it is crucial for the EU to proactively advocate for diversity, inclusion, and accurate representation within the industry. To reshape the landscape of the entertainment and film sector, the EU should champion diversity and inclusion by actively involving a varied group of storytellers, actors, directors, and producers. This approach creates a more equitable cultural environment and aligns with the EU's goal of maximising its cultural resources. By prioritising inclusive practices, the EU can foster innovation, creativity, and sustainable employment, particularly among the younger generation in the film industry. Given that the future development and sustainability of the industry hinge on the contributions of young individuals, *policies should be crafted to tap into youth's dedication, fostering creativity and nurturing a lasting interest in the European film industry.* It is imperative to initiate the establishment of a comprehensive policy framework dedicated to promoting enthusiasm for and appreciation of European films.

2. Enable involvement of young people in political decision-making

The *integration of young people into political discourse and decision-making* is of essential and future-orientated importance. It can offer innovative perspectives and approaches that are characterised by a deep familiarity with technological progress and social understanding of peers. Young people represent a multifaceted and globally connected and cosmopolitan worldview, which can ensure that political measures reflect a broad social spectrum and are geared towards long-term sustainability. Young people's engagement strengthens democratic structures and promotes social change, especially socio-cultural and political challenges. Engaging young individuals in the political process in the European film industry is therefore an investment in the development of future leaders and an adaptation of policy to the demands of a rapidly changing world governmental dynamics.

3. Create spaces for young filmmakers to experiment

Institutionalising youth development involves *creating and maintaining free spaces for experimental works primarily managed by youth themselves.* Funding, educational access, distribution, and other institutional decisions remain predominantly by adults and with their supervision. This future independence in artistic expression is crucial to ensure the authenticity and genuineness of young people's perspectives. This not only enables the work of young filmmakers to be seen more widely, but also promotes the engagement of young artists in cultural and social discourse. By providing young

people with this freedom and opportunities, the development of a diverse and dynamic film culture that integrates different voices and perspectives is supported.

4. Develop a Europe-wide approach to film education

Starting from the early stages of education, children should have the opportunity to learn and participate in meaningful discussions about movies in film clubs, delve into the processes of film production, and undertake different roles in making films in dedicated filmmaking projects. This involvement should be facilitated with the support and guidance of specialised educators. As children are growing, there is a need for options within secondary and tertiary *education that not only inspire interest but also qualify and teach young people to emerge as young professionals in all European countries.*

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Disclaimer

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Policy Brief

January 2024

Fostering 'competitiveness' and 'cultural diversity' in the European film and audiovisual sector

Evangelia Psychogiopoulou (ELIAMEP), Apostolos Samaras (ELIAMEP), Laia Comerma (ELIAMEP), Antonios Vlassis (ULIEGE), Dealan Riga (ULIEGE)

Who is this aimed at

- EU policy-makers
- national authorities
- industry stakeholders

Key messages

The European Union (EU or the Union) has sought to promote the ‘competitiveness’ of its audiovisual sector and the European film industry (EFI), which are situated at the intersection of the economy and culture, taking into account the evolving technological context and other significant changes that have occurred over the years. The EU has also sought to embed a ‘cultural diversity’ rationale into its actions targeting the EFI and the audiovisual industry.

Competitiveness and cultural diversity have long tended to be seen as reflecting, respectively, certain *market* and *non-market values* in EU policy-making. However, the two concepts have progressively become interlinked and have both proven to be of a multifaceted nature. This facilitates intricate synergies when they are combined, juxtaposed and employed together.

Competitiveness and cultural diversity can still be occasionally perceived as conflictual in EU policy-making. From this perspective, there appears to be a gap in EU policy practice in terms of finding ways to resolve possible conflicts between the two concepts. Potential conflicts are not always recognised in EU legislative and policy measures. When they are, though, reconciling solutions are rarely offered; instead one objective is given priority over the other – commonly competitiveness over cultural diversity but also vice-versa.

The EU must ensure that enhancing the competitiveness of its audiovisual industry does not come at a cost to its cultural diversity and vice-versa. This policy brief sheds some light on promising ways in which this can be achieved.

Introduction

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'European films and other audiovisual works are culturally valuable, they face strong competition from outside Europe, and they suffer from a somewhat weak circulation outside their country of origin' (European Audiovisual Observatory, 2019: 1).

The film and audiovisual industries are strongly interrelated and interdependent (Gibbons & Humphreys, 2012; Ranaivoson, Micova, Raats, 2023) as parts of the larger cultural domain. Culture was brought within the spectrum of EU competences in the early 1990s by the Treaty of Maastricht, which introduced provisions that were firmly founded on respect for cultural diversity and which also underscored the role of cultural diversity in overall EU decision-making (Craufurd Smith, 2004; Psychogiopoulou, 2008; 2021; de Witte, 2008). Until then, cultural issues had mostly been addressed in terms of the predominantly economic paradigm of the European integration process, the free movement provisions of the 1957 Treaty of Rome and the revived single market project in the wake of the Single European Act. Free movement and the internal market continue to play a crucial role in the development of the cultural and creative sectors today, following the Treaty of Lisbon, covering the EFI and the audiovisual industry. At the same time, the Treaty of Lisbon has brought important changes to the EU constitutional framework concerning culture. For instance, respect for cultural (and linguistic) diversity now features as a primary EU objective, together with safeguarding and enhancing Europe's cultural heritage. Moreover, the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU (the CFR), which has acquired binding legal force, both requires the EU institutions to respect cultural diversity in the exercise of their competences and makes respect for cultural diversity a duty of Member States when they act within the scope of EU law (Craufurd Smith, 2021).

Cultural diversity is of great value to European societies from cultural, democratic, educational, social, human rights and economic points of view. The audiovisual sector and the EFI embody Europe's common values, portray them within and outside the EU, and fulfil an indispensable role in the preservation and promotion of cultural diversity. Significantly, the audiovisual sector and the EFI are situated at the crossroads of the economy and the cultural realm. Whilst they enable the expression of cultural values, reflect the uniqueness and plurality of cultural identities in Europe and promote cultural exchange, intercultural dialogue and rapprochement, they also make key contributions to growth, innovation and competitiveness. As such, the audiovisual and film industries have a dual nature, oscillating as they do between the symbolic and material spheres and between intrinsic and market value. This raises a series of economic, social, cultural and identity-based considerations for those involved in their governance (Calligaro & Vlassis, 2017; Psychogiopoulou, 2015).

Context

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

The EU's audiovisual policy aims to promote cultural diversity, media pluralism and the free flow of audiovisual content within the EU's single market, while addressing the challenges posed by the digital transformation. It is mostly governed by Articles 167 (culture) and 173 (industry) of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU), as well as the TFEU provisions on the freedom to provide services and freedom of establishment. Key interventions in terms of EU legislative action, funding and policy ambition include: the **Audiovisual Media Services Directive (AVMSD)**,^[1] revised in 2018, which establishes rules for the free provision of audiovisual services in Europe and the promotion of European works, while also setting standards for the protection of minors and ensuring the independence of national regulatory authorities; funding programmes for the audiovisual sector, such as the **MEDIA strand of the Creative Europe Programme**,^[2] which aims to promote the development, distribution, and circulation of European audiovisual works; and the Action Plan for the media and audiovisual sectors, entitled '**Europe's Media in the Digital Decade: An Action Plan to Support Recovery and Transformation**',^[3] which focuses on the sector's post-COVID recovery and actions to embrace the digital and green transitions and to bolster dialogue with the audiovisual industry. Other policy initiatives aim to support media literacy and the European film heritage. The pressure to combine and balance the cultural and democratic aspects of the audiovisual and film sectors with their economic and industrial ones has had a marked bearing on the Union's audiovisual and film policy, which has not been static and continues to evolve (Michalis, 2014: 140). Currently, EU policy unfolds against the background of the opportunities and challenges created by the digital shift (Vlassis, 2021), with targeted efforts made to remove barriers to digital trade, facilitate cross-border access to audiovisual content, and ensure fair competition and a level-playing field among market players while taking steps to promote competitiveness and cultural diversity in the EFI and the audiovisual sector.

Existing Policy Gap

Research carried out within the REBOOT framework has shown that the concepts of 'competitiveness' and 'cultural diversity' are addressed and approached in various ways by the EU institutions. Being rich concepts in themselves, they are open to interpretation and can therefore be taken into account, framed and implemented in many different ways. However, their operationalisation is not always consistent and a policy gap appears to exist regarding the steps taken to reconcile potential conflicts between them. Although conflicts between 'competitiveness' and 'cultural diversity' are not frequently recognised, when they are, EU policy usually falls short of offering reconciling solutions and tends to prioritise one objective over the other instead. In order to avoid, contain and ultimately resolve such possible conflicts and mismatches, it is important to enrich the multi-functionality of the two concepts and take strategic aspects of both into account in their operationalisation.

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Policy recommendations

1. EU audiovisual policy should balance cultural and economic values to boost diversity and competitiveness in the digital COVID-19 era

EU audiovisual policy should meaningfully recognise the dual nature of audiovisual goods and services and hence their cultural value on the one hand and their economic value on the other, especially in the context of the digitalisation and 'platformisation' of the audiovisual industry, which the COVID-19 pandemic has accelerated. This can help increase synergies and fruitful interaction between the notions of 'cultural diversity' and 'competitiveness' in policy-making.

2. EU audiovisual policy needs a dynamic shift to actively address and speak out on competitiveness and the impact of foreign competitors in the European market, reflecting global economic realities

EU audiovisual policy has historically framed competitiveness in a distinct way which appears to overlook (or downplay) the 'foreign competitors' dimension in the EU single market. *In the light of a globalised and competitive world economy, the EU institutions and Member State authorities should adopt a more dynamic approach to (and be more outspoken about) 'competitiveness' and the need to address the disruption foreign competitors may be producing in the European audiovisual market.*

3. Enhancing the EFI and audiovisual sector's competitiveness ties closely to improving accessibility and targeting young audiences, urging the EU to focus on their unique preferences and technological engagement

Boosting the competitiveness of the EFI and the audiovisual industry is also inherently linked to questions of accessibility and audience development. Given the close connection between audiovisual policy and new technologies, in which young people play a more salient role, *the EU should pay comprehensive attention to the specific needs and preferences of younger audiences.*

4. EU policymakers should expand their focus on cultural diversity in the audiovisual sector to include both domestic and global dimensions, embracing sub-national, regional, and linguistic diversity alongside the impacts of global mobility and migration

Turning to cultural diversity, the approach taken by EU policy-makers to the notion of 'diversity' vis-à-vis the EFI and the audiovisual sector has mainly focused on strengthening and promoting cultural exchanges *between* Member States. Cultural diversity has generally been understood

horizontally, with Member States' cultural relations placed at the heart of the concept. However, *EU policy-makers should also reflect on – and develop – such 'vertical aspects' of cultural diversity as domestic diversity, sub-national relations and regional diversity (which may have a linguistic dimension) along with the cultural diversity emanating from global mobility and migration, operationalising 'diversity' in regional, territorial, linguistic and other terms.*

5. EU-level collaboration in film production and distribution is essential to showcase diverse cultures and break silos. with EU funding crucial for enhancing both internal and inter-member diversity

Increased cooperation between national and sub-national entities at the EU level at every stage of film production and distribution is crucial if cultures other than the mainstream dominant culture in each Member State are to be accounted for as part of the EU's cultural diversity. It is also key for breaking away from the narrow community shell. *EU funding instruments for the EFI and the audiovisual sector could play an important role in promoting the Union's 'diversity within' on top of its 'diversity between'.*

[1] Directive 2010/13/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 10 March 2010 on the coordination of certain provisions laid down by law, regulation or administrative action in Member States concerning the provision of audiovisual media services (Audiovisual Media Services Directive), *OJ L 95*, 15.4.2010, p. 1–24.

[2] Regulation (EU) 2021/818 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 May 2021 establishing the Creative Europe Programme (2021 to 2027) and repealing Regulation (EU) No 1295/2013, *OJ L 189*, p. 34-60.

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Policy Brief

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Pathway to the Operationalisation of the Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage: Unravelling the Copyright-Related Aspects of Populating the Data Space with Cinematographic Works

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REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

Who is this aimed at?

- EU and national policy- and law-makers

Key messages

Launched as a Union initiative in 2021, the Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage (hereinafter 'CEDS for CH' or 'CH data space') is aimed at accelerating the digitisation, online availability and digital preservation of European cultural assets that form the cultural heritage (hereinafter 'CH') of the EU Member States and play an important role in establishing a common European identity. Acknowledging that the horizontal governance structure and legislative framework to operationalise the CH data space are expected to be provided by the EU in the later stages of the initiative, the successful realisation of this vision and the population of the CH data space urges a robust roadmap that would crystallise the key actors involved in the population of CEDS for CH, the data transfers among these actors and the legal tools and incentive mechanisms to reinforce such transfers. This need is exacerbated by the specificities of the European Film Industry (hereinafter 'EFI'), the interplay of cinematographic works with copyright and the public domain, and the Union's ambitions and endeavours to digitalise and digitally preserve in-copyright and out-of-copyright elements of the European film heritage (hereinafter 'EFH').

Introduction

The CEDS for CH constitutes a landmark in the EU's cultural and digital policies and agenda dating back to the adoption of the Lisbon strategy in 2000. This strategy commenced the transition of the EU into a knowledge-based society and data-agile economy in parallel to a wave of digitisation endeavours targeting European CH assets (see: Communication COM(2001) 140 final Communication COM(2002) 263 final).

The New European Agenda for Cultural Heritage, adopted in 2018 in the European Year of Cultural Heritage, elevated CH to one of the top priorities of the EU's digital policies and advocated for the digitisation and circulation of European artworks across Europe (see: Communication COM(2018) 267 final). The pan-European efforts to enhance the digitisation and online accessibility of CH assets, eventually, paved the way for integrating the Union's digital policies concerning CH into the EU's flagship initiative: the Common European Data Space (hereinafter 'CEDS').

Launched in 2018, the CEDS aims to unleash the potential of the extensive volume of data collected and stored within the EU by facilitating the free flow and efficient use of such data across Europe (Communication COM(2018) 232 final, Communication COM(2020) 66 final). Envisaged as 'a

seamless digital area' (Communication COM(2018) 232 final), or a smoothly operating single market for data, the CEDS would realise cross-border and cross-sectoral transfers of a multitude of types of data with different levels of intensity through a trustworthy and secure digital infrastructure (Communication COM(2018) 232 final, Communication COM(2020) 66 final). The types of data referred to in this context include but are not limited to personal and non-personal, public sector and private sector, publicly-held and privately-held, publicly-funded, machine-generated, research-related, and dynamic data. Aligned with this goal, the idea of establishing a CEDS requires innovative ways to incentivise, accelerate and legitimise data transfers within a complex network consisting not only of Government-to-Government (hereinafter 'G2G') but also Business-to-Government (hereinafter 'B2G') and Business-to-Business (hereinafter 'B2B') cooperation and data flows, also in terms of boosting the European market power and share by opening the use of such data for the development of new products and services.

Constituting one of the domain-specific data spaces incorporating the CEDS, the CH data space provides a single digital space – or, for the time being, a single internet platform – that hosts and facilitates the reuse of digital(ised) CH assets (Recommendation (EU) 2021/1970). To do so, the EC has entrusted the Consortium previously assigned to operationalise the renowned digital library of the EU: Europeana. The role that Europeana plays in the CEDS for CH is two-pronged. While the realisation of this data space relies on the Europeana Consortium's expertise in the field, CH data space is built upon the legacy of the Europeana project as Europeana's digital collections and the online platform to disseminate these collections will constitute, respectively, the input for and the hosting platform of the CEDS for CH.

Yet, a complicated task awaits the Europeana Consortium, especially from the perspective of the EFI. Whereas the Union's cultural agenda draws attention to the digitisation, online accessibility and digital preservation of the EFH, the Commission Recommendation of 10 November 2021 reveals that only 2,47% of Europeana's assets comprise audiovisual content (Recommendation (EU) 2021/1970). The percentage of cinematographic works within this 2,47 % has not been revealed within the document; however, what is made explicit is that only 45% of the overall Europeana assets are reusable (Recommendation (EU) 2021/1970).

Statement of the problem

The launch of the CEDS for CH revolutionised the legal discourse centred around CH assets for it placed them at the intersection of copyright law, data law, and CH law – legal disciplines that have originated from disparate policy objectives and evolved independently by following different paths. Yet, standing at the crossroads of these three disciplines, the challenges imposed by the CEDS for CH are multifaceted and require multi-disciplinary approaches to help unfold their layers while unveiling the policy and legislative gaps that necessitate action at the Union and national levels.

This policy brief focuses on the *preliminary* questions to be addressed from a copyright-oriented standpoint while leaving the intricacies stemming from data and CH laws to prospective policy briefs. In so doing, it concentrates on the interaction of *merely* cinematographic works or excerpts thereof with the CH data space.

Cinematographic works have been the subject of a multitude of Union policies, including the preservation of CH, revitalisation of EFI and the modernisation of the EU copyright law. Having approached their subject-matter from different angles through the lens of different disciplines, the terminology adopted in several EU documents obscures the meaning of cinematographic works, if not clash with that of the international copyright regime. Furthermore, the CEDS for CH merges the Union's cultural and digital policies without necessarily bringing clarity to the interaction of this initiative with the ongoing efforts in the digital agenda revolving around the EFH.

The definitional opacity and the lack of clarity on the Union's vision on the interaction of EFH with the CH data space complicate the identification of the legal tools and mechanisms that would help achieve the digitisation, online availability and digital preservation of EFI.

Policy Recommendations

1. Reconciliation of the definitions associated with 'cinematographic works' in international legal instruments and the EU documents

The EU copyright *acquis* does not define the concepts of work or cinematographic work. Nevertheless, several EU documents introducing the Union's cultural, digital and media policies and agenda use inconsistent terminology or use certain terminology interchangeably which eventually causes opacity in the EU policy- and law-makers' approach to and regulation of cinematographic works, especially when compared to the foundational instruments of international copyright law.

- **Cinematographic works**

The Recommendation of 16 November 2005 articulates cinematographic works as 'moving-image material of any length, in particular, cinematographic fiction, cartoons and documentaries, which is *intended to be shown in cinemas*'^[1] (Recommendation 2005/865/CE).

Whereas the underpinnings of such a formulation are unknown, this definition is neither compatible with the established norms and standards of international and EU copyright law nor with the Union's general digital policies.

Regarding the copyright-related aspects, it shall be noted that copyright law approaches its subject-matter (e.g. literary or artistic works) by associating the work with its author/creator rather than its target audience. Accordingly, it centralises the intellectual creation, which is the expression of an idea; and it entitles the author/creator of an intellectual creation of such expression, in principle, if it is original, in the sense that 'it is the author's own intellectual creation'^[2]. In line with this principle, Article 2(1) of the Berne Convention refers to cinematographic works as a sub-category of literary and artistic works. And stipulates that:

'[t]he expression "literary and artistic works" shall include *every production* in the literary, scientific and artistic domain, whatever may be the mode or form of its expression, such as (...) *cinematographic works to which are assimilated works expressed by a process analogous to cinematography* (...).'^[3]

However, by reducing cinematographic work to a means of mass entertainment, the Recommendation excludes a significant portion of original works acknowledged as copyright-protected cinematographic works (e.g. born-digital films produced for video-on-demand or DVD industry) from the globally accepted description of the term.

As to the Union's overall digital policies, this approach implies the existence of a cultural valorisation scheme which ranks cinematographic works produced for the primary window of cinema (i.e. movie theatres) higher than those produced for the secondary windows (e.g. television broadcasts, video-on-demand platforms, online-content sharing platforms). Nevertheless, the inevitable impact of the technology and internet on the production and dissemination of cultural content has been one of the justifications for the Union's policies and legislative endeavours to support and facilitate the accessibility and use of digital cultural content, as evidenced by the Regulation (EU) 2017/1128 on the portability of online content services.

- **Cinematographic works v. Audiovisual content**

The terminology adopted within the EU copyright and media instruments adds to the terminological opacity (see: Poll, 2002). Indeed, Directive 2006/115/EC employs the term 'film' as an umbrella category that encompasses cinematographic works; it defines films as 'a cinematographic or audiovisual work or moving images, whether or not accompanied by sound'. Neither this Directive nor any others offer any indicators of the difference between cinematographic works, audiovisual works or moving images. However, Directive 93/83/EEC and Directive 2006/116/EC use cinematographic works

and audiovisual works interchangeably while Directive 2001/29/EC, in line with the international copyright instruments, employs a new term: first fixation of films, without necessarily defining it. On top of all these, Directive 2010/13/EU refers to cinematographic works, audiovisual works and films as separate categories of cultural content.

- **Cinematographic works v. Works of visual art**

Last but not least, Article 14 of the Directive (EU) 2019/790 contains a legal provision that is pivotal to the reuse of digital copies of cinematographic works that have fallen into the public domain. This provision, however, employs the term ‘works of visual art’ which has not been defined or used before in the EU copyright legislation or related documents. Neither the international copyright instruments use or define this term, whereas a broad interpretation of the term would encompass cinematographic works (Benabou et al., 2020; Rosati, 2021).

Against this background, the EU legislative framework would benefit from the EU’s intervention to crystallise the differences between such concepts used in the EU copyright and media legislation and to streamline the use of such concepts vis-à-vis international legal instruments.

2. Clarification of the expectations at the Union and national levels regarding the interplay of cinematographic works with the Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage

The Commission Recommendation of 10 November 2021 consists of quantitative data, annexed to the main document, which reflects on the total sum of the digital records held by each Member State as of 2021 as well as the short-term and long-term indicative targets to be achieved in digitisation of cultural assets, respectively, by 2025 and 2030. Having such clear goals surely provides the EU with opportunities to accelerate and monitor the progress of the digitisation activities at the national level, as the latter would eventually facilitate the operationalisation of the CEDS for CH. Nevertheless, once the features unique to cinematographic works are taken into account, it becomes inevitable to complement these quantitative goals with qualitative ones that would guide the digitisation endeavours of the Member States.

Whereas the Union’s policies on the digitisation and online availability of CH assets have mainly targeted public domain materials, neither the Union’s cultural agenda nor the definitions embraced by the Union documents construe or decrease CH to a set of archival cultural assets that are no longer protected by copyright.^[4] Yet, the interplay of copyright with cinematographic works complicates the ambitions of the Union and the Member States to digitise and disseminate digital copies of cinematographic works or excerpts thereof via the CEDS for CH.

Cinematographic works are usually joint-authored works. The term of copyright protection granted upon cinematographic works lasts during the lifetime of its authors and 70 years post-mortem, which shall be calculated from the death of the last surviving person who was involved in the creation of the work either as the principal director, the author of the screenplay, the author of the dialogue or the composer of music specifically created for use in the work (Directive 2006/116/EC). Considered along with the invention of cinematography in the 1890s, it could be presumed that a significant portion of the cinematographic works that are essential to the European CH still enjoy copyright protection.

It is also worth noting that the audiovisual assets available on the Europeana platform are mostly composed of excerpts of television broadcasts, whereas there is no concrete evidence to suggest that Europeana collections include cinematographic works or their excerpts. Neither there is evidence to clarify whether the Union or the Europeana Consortium have ever aimed to make cinematographic works available on this online platform.

In this sense, the Member States and the custodial and memory institutions across Europe would benefit from a prospectus that would crystallise the Union's expectations concerning the digitalisation, online accessibility and preservation of European cinematographic works vis-à-vis the Union policies centred around the preservation of the European film heritage.

3. Mitigating the digitisation of cinematographic works of the public domain: Setting up guidelines on the interpretation and application of Article 14 of the Directive (EU) 2019/790 to the digitalised cinematographic works

Article 14 of Directive (EU) 2019/790, for the first time in the EU legislative history, introduced a legal provision directly addressed to the public domain. This provision requires EU Member States to take the necessary measures to protect the public domain by preventing the revival of legal protection over the copies of reproduced works of visual art.

The provision stipulates that 'when the term of protection of a work of visual art has expired, any material resulting from an act of reproduction of that work is not subject to copyright or related rights unless the material resulting from that act of reproduction is original in the sense that it is the author's own intellectual creation'. The act of reproduction as such shall be understood in broad terms, as suggested by a multitude of EU Directives (see: Directive 96/9/EC, Directive 2001/29/EC, Directive 2009/24/EC; also see: Rosati, 2021). Therefore, the reproduction as such can go beyond a faithful reproduction of the public domain material, and it can be 'direct or indirect, temporary or permanent, by any means and in any form (e.g. two- or three-dimensional reproductions, analogue or digital reproductions, etc.), in whole or in part' (Rosati, 2021).

Whereas this legal provision was transposed, vastly, *verbatim* into Member States' national copyright laws (see: *Copyright Flexibilities*, 2023), its interpretation by the Court of Justice of the EU and application by the national courts are yet to be seen. Nevertheless, many scholarly works already flag the possible outcomes of the interaction of this provision with the digital reproduction of cultural assets.

In the meantime, the applicability of this provision to the digital copies of out-of-copyright cinematographic works fixated on analogue media remains unresolved. In practice, the digitisation of content as such is often accompanied by certain other actions, for instance, restoration of the film, colourisation (also of originally black and white films), adjustment of the saturation and tinting, dubbing, insertion of subtitles and synchronisation of the audio and subtitles (see: Bader, 1986; Op den Kamp, 2018). Nevertheless, there is no precedent set, especially in the EU copyright law, whether these acts, which modify the original work, lead to the creation of a derivative work eligible for copyright protection.

Against this background, the Union endeavours to preserve European film heritage, also given the Union's aim to digitise 'all public domain masterpieces' (Recommendation 2011/711/EU), would benefit from legal clarity on the application of Article 14 of the Directive (EU) 2019/790 to the cinematographic works that have fallen into the public domain.

4. Planning the way ahead: Introducing a legislative framework for the governance structure for the Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage

By no means overlooking the fact that the CEDS for CH is at its earliest stages, especially compared to the formerly launched data spaces, such as the European Health Data Space (hereinafter 'EHDS'), the successful operationalisation of CH data space requires a robust roadmap and a legislative framework that would provide a governance structure tailored to this roadmap.

At the time being, the CEDS for CH gives the impression of being an advanced model of the Europeana platform. Indeed, the CH data space initiative is administered by the Expert Group led by the Europeana Consortium, and it builds upon Europeana's digital collection efforts and cultural assets while also aimed at disseminating these assets via the Europeana platform. This reality blurs the lines that differentiate the CEDS for CH initiative from that of Europeana (also see: Keller, 2021).

Furthermore, the existing EU documents on the CEDS for CH encourage EU Member States to take measures that would help populate the Europeana platform. Nevertheless, the vision of CEDS, which is expected to be shared by all the domain-specific data spaces, dwells upon data transfers between a complex network of multiple stakeholders, including those of B2G and B2B data transfers – and not just for non-commercial but also for commercial purposes. Nevertheless, the current scheme

envisages CEDS for CH to flow through a thin horizontal line connecting Europeana to data aggregators connected to public cultural heritage institutions and galleries, libraries, archives and museums. This system not only eliminates the vertical lines expected to connect public and private institutions as well as end-users, but it also overlooks the fact that CH assets are held or owned by private custodial and memory institutions or other private actors.

Despite its inauguration in 2021, the CEDS for CH would still benefit from a robust legislative framework setting up the network of public and private actors to be involved in the operationalisation of this data space and regulating the data transfers among the actors to be involved in the population of this data space (also see: Islam et al., 2022; Niccolucci et al., 2022), as has been done by the proposed Regulation for EHDS.^[5]

Such an endeavour would, initially, require a meticulous assessment of the EU copyright *acquis* and the pan-European copyright landscape to contemplate their capacity to facilitate the digital reproduction of in-copyright elements of CH as well as the communication and making available to the public of digitised CH assets, especially in the aftermath of the transposition of Directive (EU) 2019/790. Indeed, the European copyright discourse would benefit from an up-to-date and comprehensive analysis of the opportunities provided and challenges imposed by the EU and national copyright laws on the operationalisation of the CEDS for CH, which would reflect on the impact of Directive 2012/28/EU on the digitisation of orphan works and the extended collective license schemes enshrined in Article 8 of Directive (EU) 2019/790 on the digitisation of out-of-commerce works. It is also essential to collect and analyse empirical evidence on the possible impacts of copyright exceptions and limitations (hereinafter 'E&Ls'), which are envisioned only for non-commercial uses, on the public and private partnerships to be established for large-scale digitisation projects, such as CEDS for CH.

With respect to the outcomes of such research activities, the horizontal governance structure to be enacted for the CH data space would be able to elaborate on the public and private entities to be involved in the operationalisation of this data space, to augment the existing copyright tools or to introduce a new set of E&Ls or compulsory licensing schemes to enable the digitisation of the cornerstones of the European CH, including those of EFH.

[1] Emphasis added.

[2] This phrase has been embraced by the cornerstones of the EU copyright *acquis* in order to define the originality criterion sought for copyright protection. See: Directive 96/9/EC, Art. 3(1), Directive 2009/24/EC, Art. 1(3); Directive (EU) 2019/790, Art. 14.

[3] Emphasis added.

[4] The Commission Recommendation of 10 November 2021, while explaining the purpose and scope of this instrument in its Article 1, embraces a broad articulation of CH by encompassing ‘all types of cultural heritage (tangible, intangible, natural, born-digital)’ (Recommendation (EU) 2021/1970). In the same line, Article 2 thereof refers to ‘archival documents’ as an example clustered under tangible CH. The EU’s approach to CH therein is not only aligned with the UNESCO Convention for the Safeguarding of Intangible Cultural Heritage and the Council of Europe Framework Convention on the Value of Cultural Heritage for Society, both of which acknowledge CH as a dynamic rather than a static phenomenon, but also the Union’s policies addressed to the population of the Europeana platform. The Commission Staff Working Paper, released in 2008, clarifies that the Europeana platform initially aims to digitise and make available online the content allocated to the public domain, while the dissemination of more actual content protected by copyright is also within the agenda (Commission Staff Working Paper SEC(2008) 2372).

[5] See: Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the European Health Data Space, COM/2022/197 final.

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The background information provided herein as well as the policy recommendation addressed to the EU and national policy- and law-makers are extracted from the book chapter, entitled 'A Panoptic View of the Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage Through the Lens of the European Film Industry', drafted by Caterina Sganga and Pelin Turan for the edited volume to be published by the end of the REBOOT project as part of Deliverable 7.5 (Scientific publications).

This policy brief, focusing on copyright-related aspects of the topic of choice, comprises the first part of this endeavour and will be complemented by a second part focusing on the data law-related aspects

and a third one focusing on the cultural heritage law-related aspects of the operationalisation of the CEDS for CH.

This policy brief does not reflect the views of the European Union or any of its agencies or bodies. The information included herein is the outcome of the scientific research conducted by the authors and reflects the views of the authors only.

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Policy Brief

January 2024

Developing young people's Engagement with European Cinema via the Youth Audience Award

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REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

Who is this aimed at

- managers at the European Film Academy and policymakers
- officers responsible for film at the European Commission

Key messages

The European Film Academy's Young Audience Award (YAA) is an important film prize that deserves wider recognition and appreciation among diverse audiences, filmmakers, producers, educators, and policymakers. The YAA has great potential to promote European youth films, pay attention to young people as an important audience segment, promote multilingualism and cultural diversity in Europe, and build competencies for future European film professionals. The European Film Academy has ambitious plans to develop these activities in the future. Better communication, promotion, and funding are likely to increase the YAA's impact on the European film industry and boost young people's engagement with European cinema.

Introduction

The competitiveness of the European film industry relies on audiences interested in viewing European films. The European Film Academy seeks to build future competitiveness of the European film industry by engaging young people as audiences of European cinema through the YAA. The YAA is a category of the European Film Awards, supported by the EU through its Creative Europe Media programme. The Academy has awarded YAAs to European films since 2012. Young people aged 12–14 years from 42 European countries, plus Israel, Palestine, and Australia, form the juries that choose the winner.

Besides being a film award, the YAA selection process is a transnational, constantly evolved film initiative including social, cultural, and film-industry-focused aims. Over the years, there have been major changes in the selection procedure of three nominated films, increasing the role and agency of the young people in the process. In 2020, the European Film Academy started to develop a European Film Club as a platform linking the YAA jury members and film and cinema professionals. The social and cultural aims of the YAA are reflected in educational materials that the European Film Academy has provided for the young jury members and their teachers since 2017.

Statement of the problem

Despite the EU's dedication to promote European cinema to create future audiences, there is still little academic research on young Europeans' conceptions about and attitudes toward European cinema. Previous research also includes some contradictory results. Soto-Sanfiel et al. have indicated that European youth prefer US cinema and have a stereotypical image of European films considering them more intellectual, artistic, boring, and of lower quality compared to US cinema (Soto-Sanfiel et al., 2018, 2021). Veenstra et al. have shown that young Belgians prefer US films to European ones and national films to other European films. They point out that structural limitations affect the film viewing practices, especially among young people. The current infrastructure favours Hollywood productions and that is what audiences all over Europe like to watch. National cinemas poorly circulate in Europe (Veenstra et al., 2022). These results resonate with Mitric's study (2022) indicating that young European audiences prefer films in which the characters speak either their mother tongue or English.

Soto-Sanfiel et al. (2018, 2021) have shown that film paedagogical activities do not significantly impact or change the students' attitudes to European cinema while Mitric's (2022) research indicated that film literacy education may promote the reception and consumption of European arthouse cinema and, thus, increase its social and economic impact through extended audiences.

The previous studies suggest that European cinema needs to be promoted to young audiences more effectively. The YAA has great potential in this regard, especially through its paedagogical elements and attempts to engage young people with European cinema, but the award and the awarded films suffer from poor visibility.

Context

This policy brief is based on a study conducted in the REBOOT project in spring 2023 (Hiltunen & Lähdesmäki, 2023). The study aimed at exploring how the European Film Academy seeks to build the future competitiveness of the European film industry by engaging young people as audiences of European cinema and to analyse the preferences of 12–14-year-old cinema audiences in Europe through the YAA.

The data of the study consisted of the eleven YAA winning films, the European Film Academy's website, the educational materials about the YAA winning films, an online meeting with the representatives of the European Film Academy, and email interviews with one of them. The research was conducted using the methods of thematic analysis of the films and critical close reading of the other material.

The thematic analysis of the winning films revealed three, broad, and partly overlapping themes that recurred in the stories of the films: coming of age, belonging, social challenges. The success of

dramas and serious content may seem surprising, because a large part of mainstream children's and youth films are action-packed adventures, especially in Hollywood productions.

Existing Policy Gap

During the years, the European Commission has sought to tackle the poor productivity of the European film industry by launching new strategies and policies. In the EU strategy on European film in the digital era, the Commission notes how 63% of all films released in the EU in 2012 were European, but only 33% of the admissions came from European films, while US productions accounted for 20% of releases and 65% of admissions (EC, 2014). There haven't been any major changes in the productivity of European productions. In 2021, for instance, the market share by US productions in the EU was 58%, while European films dropped from the record high of 39% in 2020 to 27%, being in line with levels before the Covid-19 pandemic (Cabrera Blázquez et al., 2023).

Awarding prizes is a common practice impacting diverse societal sectors, including film, in today's attention economy. There is an increasing number of film awards hosted by local, regional, national, and transnational actors. Film awards are a tool to impact the sector by raising interest towards the awarded films and bringing the prize-giving organisations to the spotlight and promoting their goals and value discourses. Film awards are brands, and the brands have power only when they are strong enough – i.e., when they are broadly recognised, competed for, and appreciated among film professionals and audiences.

The strategies and policies of the European film industry lack concrete measures to link the productivity of the European film industry, film awards, the communication and branding of (awarded) European films, and the engagement of young people with European cinema.

Policy recommendations

Despite its limited scope, this study has several policy implications.

1. The YAA could be better utilised for increasing young people's engagement with European cinema

The YAA has great potential for engaging young people with European cinema. The European Film Academy has already taken steps to broaden the YAA initiative by enabling 15–19-year-old teenagers' involvement via the recently established European Film Club.

The pedagogical material of the YAA could be developed into a European film literacy learning programme that utilises the best practices and lessons learned from previous film literacy programmes created in European (see e.g., European Film Factory 2023) and national projects (see e.g., Mitric, 2022 for the Danish initiative of Med Skolen i Biografen/School Cinema and JEF n.d. for promoting film

literacy in Belgium; see EFAD n.d. for examples of national film education initiatives). A European-level film literacy learning programme could have intertwined cultural and social aims. The social themes and topics recurring in the YAA films support including such aims in the learning programme. An open-access research-based pedagogical learning programme could strengthen the platform and benefit various stakeholders more broadly, namely students and teachers in formal and informal educational institutions who do not participate in the YAA awarding process and are not members of the European Film Club.

2. The YAA could be better communicated

The European Film Academy, European youth film producers, and the broad audience interested in youth films might benefit from a more transparent awarding process at the YAA. The YAA has great potential to advance the genre of youth film and the notion of young people as an important audience segment. This potential can be fulfilled through better public communication and promotion of the YAA and the awarded films. The EU's long-term support for communication and promotion activities is crucial.

3. The YAA films could be better accessed via VOD platforms

Better access increases YAA films' recognition and may increase their social and economic impact through extended audiences. The lack of a common European VOD platform(s) is a major challenge that the EU needs to address soon. The total admissions of the YAA films as reported in European Audiovisual Observatory's Lumiere database reveal that the films' distribution is limited to a small number of European countries and that most of each film's theatre admissions are domestic.

4. The YAA films could be made more accessible via translation

The accessibility of the YAA films would increase through multilingual subtitles and/or dubbing. The EU could support the translation of subtitles for the YAA films, as it does with the films awarded the LUX Audience Prize. Multilingual subtitling promotes linguistic and cultural diversity in Europe.

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